

Student's Attitude towards Sustainable Development

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to determine the significant difference in the attitudes of students towards sustainable development when analyzed according to their gender, religion, and age. The study employed the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-comparative method, and convenience sampling with Mean, t-test, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) as statistical tools. Researchers used adapted and validated survey questionnaires in gathering the data from the 86 target respondents. The results revealed that the attitude towards sustainable development among students is notably high, indicating a solid manifestation of these attitudes. Interestingly, there were significant differences in attitudes based on gender, but no significant differences were found concerning religion and age. These findings suggest that attitudes toward sustainability based on gender differ, while factors like religion and age do not significantly differ. The study emphasizes the importance of integrating sustainable development education into school curriculums to cultivate a generation aware and proactive about sustainability issues. This research contributes to promoting environmental consciousness early, highlighting the pivotal role of education in shaping a sustainable future.

KEY WORDS: Attitude, sustainable development, students, quantitative research

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly evolving world, sustainable development has become one of the twenty-first century's most pressing and sensitive issues. As society continues to prioritize economic growth and development, excessive consumption and expansion have led to the depletion and degradation of resources, environmental destruction, pollution, and global warming. These ecological issues have become critical global challenges (Andersen, 2018; Choi, 2010; UNESCO, 2005). Strengthening education to raise awareness and understanding of sustainable development is essential to address these issues effectively.

Sustainability is increasingly becoming a priority for organizations and countries at all levels. It emphasizes the need to preserve our present resources for the benefit of future generations. This effort involves everyone including corporate entities, educational institutions, households, and government organizations all working towards sustainable development. UNESCO's three pillars of sustainable development, economic, social, and environmental, are gaining traction as more people recognize their importance. This holistic approach, which looks at these dimensions together, is supported by research from Michalos (2012), Olsson et al. (2016), and UNESCO (2005). Their work highlights how interconnected and interdependent these facets are, showing that we must consider the impact on all three areas to meet our needs now and in the future. This interconnectedness is crucial for effectively addressing local and global challenges (UNESCO, 2009).

In addition, numerous studies have been conducted in recent decades in response to environmental issues, leading to a shift in how people view the relationship between humans and nature. Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has received increased attention as a crucial field for promoting the principles of sustainable development (Cotton, 2007; Michalos, 2012; Olsso et al., 2016; Tilbury, 2012). ESD aims to equip individuals with the knowledge, skills, and values to create a sustainable future. According to Boeve-de Pauw et al. (2015), ESD affects students' knowledge about the prerequisites for sustainable development and their self-reported sustainability behavior.

Over the years, several studies have shown that the concern about contributing to the development of sustainable practices varies according to gender. The gender constitutes a key demographic variable that are often associated with varying perspectives and attitudes towards various socio-economic issues. For example, in relation to sustainability, a concept intertwined with sustainable development, gender has been found to contribute to differences in perceptions and attitudes (Soetanto et al., 2017; Calabrese et al., 2016). These differences may be due to the model of basic human values. Also, it revealed that while men had more environmental knowledge, women had more substantial environmental commitments and feelings.

On top of that, sustainable development has increasingly become a focal point in global education, particularly for younger generations aged 11-16. Understanding the attitudes of this demographic towards sustainability is critical, as these individuals will

soon be at the forefront of environmental stewardship and decision-making. (Roczen, 2013) demonstrated that adolescents' pro-environmental attitudes significantly motivate sustainable behaviors, suggesting that early educational interventions can foster a lifelong commitment to sustainability.

Also, the link between religion and sustainable development is complex and complicated. Religion is one of the most significant and widespread social structures; it influences and shapes almost every aspect of culture and society. According to the Pew Research Centre, approximately 84% of people identify as religious (Pew Research Centre 2017). The idea of religion is complex, contentious, and often even vague. It is reasonable to break down religion into various pieces to understand the relationship between religion and development and the related causal processes. The concept of a multifaceted understanding of religion is not new (e.g., Barro and McCleary 2003; Campante and Yanagizawa-Drott 2015; Feess et al. 2014). However, the events that transpired did not conform to this prediction. Most countries maintain consistently high levels of self-reported religiosity, religious identification, and practice, indicating that the globe has not become increasingly secular. More than 80% of people on the planet were followers of a religion in 2015, and estimates suggest that percentage will rise.

However, effectiveness of "education" must be relied upon by its proponents. Children may feel, care for, and be aware of their surroundings from an early age when relevant concepts are first introduced. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of the United Nations still depend heavily on teacher education (Leal Filho, 2018). UNESCO (2014) stressed that the key to adopting and applying ESD policy is teacher education. ESD is essential in equipping aspiring educators to impart knowledge about sustainable development to others (Ferreira, 2007). In order to prepare today's teachers for tomorrow's sustainability, it is strategic to incorporate ESD into teacher education programs. Unfortunately, most instructors have little to no awareness of sustainability, and teacher education institutes typically do not include coursework that can increase sustainability knowledge (Merritt, 2019).

Furthermore, this article the Consumers towards the Goals of Sustainable Development: Attitudes and Typology aims to assess consumer attitudes toward the idea, presumptions, and principles of sustainable development, as well as consumer knowledge of these categories (including sustainable consumption), focusing on the differences among respondents' respective generations. Based on their adoption of 17 SDGs, the immediate successors of the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), also known as Agenda 2030, the authors seek to differentiate largely homogenous consumer groupings. Other UNESCO initiatives, such as the United Nations Decade of Education for SD (UNESCO Citation 2005) Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), also commonly known as Agenda 2030, were carried out to enhance and encourage the integration of ESD into educational policies and educational action plans across all member nations globally. Improvements in student learning and development, as well as the promotion of ESD, are all facilitated by teacher education (Al-Zbun, 2016; Faulkner, 2017; McKeown, 2014).

This study is anchored to Ajzen's The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB), a theoretical framework that can be used to comprehend people's attitudes and behaviors, including attitudes toward sustainable development. Researchers can examine how attitudes, arbitrary norms, and perceived behavioral control influence people's intentions to engage in sustainable behaviors by using the TPB to examine the study on attitudes toward sustainable development. The results can be used to pinpoint essential variables that affect how people feel about sustainable development and to inform the creation of interventions that encourage pro-environmental beliefs and actions, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Beliefs about the likely outcomes of the behavior (behavioral beliefs), normative beliefs about what other people should expect from us, and control beliefs about the existence of factors that may help or hinder the behavior (control beliefs) are the three types of considerations that shape human behavior (Ajzen, 2019).

Additionally, another basis for this study is the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) Theory used in several fields, such as environmental psychology, conservation, and sustainability studies. It offers a framework for comprehending how societal norms, individual values, and environmental attitudes influence people's conduct. Understanding these dynamics will help academics and professionals create treatments and methods to support sustainable practices and pro-environmental behavior. The VBN theory was developed to understand human green/sustainable consumption behavior. The VBN hypothesis expands on the NAM to explain why people behave pro-environmentally (Choi, 2015; Han, 2020).

After describing the study's context and defining its research question, the conceptual framework identifies one variable—attitude toward sustainable development—as a key component. Participants' attitudes or behaviors toward sustainable development in four domains (the environment, society, economy, and education) were assessed using a cross-sectional study about their age, gender, and religion.

This aims to study the attitude towards sustainable development of 6th-grade students based on their demographic profile below. The researchers did not find any studies related to attitudes towards sustainable development, especially among elementary school students, as respondents on this topic in the Philippines, which is an extremely important period due to the growing population. As a result, this research can help generate new understanding. Communities, students, and even families can benefit from the data of this study, knowing the importance of attitudes toward sustainable development. Furthermore, this research will help students have the right attitude towards sustainable development.

The Role of Early Childhood Education for a Sustainable Society took place in Göteborg, Sweden, in May 2007 and featured contributions from delegates from sixteen countries. More significantly, it focuses on early childhood education and how it may help create a sustainable society. Early childhood education is the initial stage of education when the basis for lifetime learning and

growth is set. UNESCO (2008) is pleased to publish it since it provides a unique and priceless collection of insights on the connections between early education and sustainable development. As the beliefs, attitudes, behaviors, and abilities learned at this time may have a lasting effect on later life, they must start in early childhood. Thus, it is evident that early childhood education is essential in attempts to promote sustainable development.

On the other hand, this study aims to determine significant difference in the attitude of sixth-grade students towards sustainable development when analyzed according to gender, religion, and age. It sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 gender;
 - 1.2 religion; and
 - 1.3 age?
2. What is the level of attitude towards sustainable development?
3. Is there a significant difference in the attitude towards sustainable development when categorized according to their demographic profile?

The purpose of this study was to determine the attitude towards sustainable development of grade 6 students. The significance of this research extends to several key stakeholders. For the students themselves, the study will help foster greater consciousness and awareness about the importance of sustainable development as they look towards the future. Additionally, the study stands to benefit the students' parents, as they play a critical role in shaping their children's attitudes and instilling positive values around sustainability.

The findings are also highly valuable for the teachers at the school, as the study will enable them to better understand their students' perspectives on sustainable development. This knowledge can then inform the educational approaches and responses they implement to address any gaps or needs.

Finally, this study may also serve as a useful resource and reference for future researchers exploring this topic. The data and insights provided can inform the design of subsequent studies, while also offering a comparative baseline for examining the evolving nature of sustainability attitudes over time.

METHODOLOGY

Research Respondents

The research respondents of this study are the Grade 6 students of Angel Villarica Central Elementary School. The researchers chose eighty-six (86) respondents using convenience sampling. The researchers chose 86 students using convenience sampling. Convenience sampling was used since respondents were ready and available to be studied (Creswell, 2012, cited in Alabi, 2017). Several researches suggest that if parametric tests are to be employed 30 – 500 subjects would be the necessary sample size (Ross, 2020; cited in Bacala et al., 2024).

Materials and Instruments

A set of questionnaire was adapted from the study of Biasutti and Frate (2017), which were validated by experts in questionnaire construction. The adapted standardized questionnaire is valid in contents as it underwent a series of modifications to classify the most reliable and valid questions. Further, it was already tested and proven by the authors per se. The questionnaire was designed in a very comprehensive form with the help of expert validators to provide the respondents with ease and comfort in answering each question and understanding the study's objective. The instrument is intended to measure the attitude of the students towards sustainable development with subscales of environment (5 items), economy (5 items), society (5 items), and education (5 items). This 20-item survey utilized a 5-point Likert type scale (from Very Low to Very High).

Design and Procedure

Research Design. This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative, descriptive-comparative method of research to determine the student's attitude towards sustainable development. The differences in the level of attitude towards sustainable development when analyzed according to their demographic profile were also sought. Descriptive-comparative method of research aims to observe and describe the variations between different groups in a population without intentionally changing any factors (Cantrell, 2011, cited in Villaabrille et al., 2024; Poliquit et al., 2024; Camino et al., 2023).

Data Collection. The researchers sought approval from the Dean of College and Schools Division Superintendent, after the approval, the letter was sent to the School Principal prior to the administration of the research instruments. Consent was also sought from the respondents for voluntary participation. Respondents were given ample time to complete the tool. Retrieval on the said instrument was done immediately after the respondents answered the tool completely. After gathering the necessary data, these were tabulated, subjected to statistical treatment, and interpreted accordingly.

Statistical Tools. The following statistical tools were employed in this study:

Mean. This was used to determine the level of attitude towards sustainable development among sixth-grade students.

t-test for Independent Samples. This was used to determine the significant difference in the attitude towards sustainable development among students when analyzed according to gender and age.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). This was used to determine the significant difference in the attitude towards sustainable development among students when analyzed according to religion.

Ethical Considerations. The researchers ensured that the study was conducted with adherence to ethical standards. It followed protocol and underwent examination. To ensure ethical considerations were met, the researchers followed the necessary processes in conducting the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the respondents. The survey comprised 86 sixth-grade students, distributed in terms of gender, religion, and age. According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB); individual attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence behavioral intentions. In the context of the demographic distribution of respondents, the higher percentage of female students (61.6%) compared to male students (38.4%) may indicate differing attitudes towards sustainable development. TPB suggests that gender differences can impact attitudes and intentions towards sustainability, with females potentially exhibiting stronger positive attitudes towards sustainable practices. In line with the Value-Belief-Norm (VBN) theory, personal values, beliefs, and norms shape behavior. The distribution of students across different religions: Roman Catholic (51.2%), Non-Catholic Christians and Protestants (39.5%), and Islam (9.3%) reflect varying value systems and norms related to sustainability. VBN emphasizes that religious beliefs and values can influence individuals' attitudes and behaviors toward sustainable development, with students from different religious backgrounds potentially exhibiting distinct perspectives on environmental issues. Moreover, the age distribution among respondents: 11-year-old (54.7%), 12-year-old, and above (45.3%) is crucial in the context of both TPB and VBN. TPB suggests that age can affect perceived behavioral control and intentions toward sustainable practices, with younger students potentially being more open to adopting sustainable behaviors. VBN highlighted that age-related values and norms can shape individuals' attitudes toward sustainability, with younger students possibly being more receptive to environmental values and norms. By integrating the TPB and VBN theories into the analysis of the demographic data, this study can provide a comprehensive understanding of how individual attitudes, beliefs, and norms influenced by gender, religion, and age impact the attitudes and behaviors toward sustainable development among sixth-grade students. This approach can offer valuable insights into the complex interplay between individual characteristics and sustainable behaviors, guiding the development of effective educational interventions to promote sustainability within the school community.

Table 1. Characteristics of 86 students included in the survey

Profile Variables	f	%
Gender		
Male	33	38.4
Female	53	61.6
Religion		
Roman Catholic	44	51.2
Non-Catholic Christians & Protestants	34	39.5
Islam	8	9.3
Age		
11 years old	47	54.7
12 years old & above	39	45.3

Attitude towards Sustainable Development

As shown in the table below, the overall mean (\bar{x} =4.17, SD =.487) was described as high. This means that the student's attitude towards sustainable development is oftentimes manifested. This implies that the students often prioritize sustainable development in their attitudes and behaviors. It also implies that they firmly commit to environmental stewardship, social equity, and economic prosperity for present and future generations. This reflects a collective awareness and proactive engagement in addressing global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and social inequality. It indicates that students recognize the interconnectedness of environmental, social, and economic issues and actively advocate for sustainable solutions to build a more resilient and equitable world. UNESCO (2017) outlines the importance of integrating sustainable development goals into education to empower students with the knowledge and skills necessary for addressing global challenges. This supports the observation that students hold a strong commitment to sustainable development.

Looking at each indicator closely, *society* as a dimension of attitude toward sustainable development got the highest mean score of 4.40 or very high. This implies that students consistently view sustainable development as a comprehensive approach integrating

social justice, global collaboration, cultural understanding, and equitable access to essential services, promoting both individual welfare and collective progress. This attitude reflects a comprehensive understanding that sustainable development is fundamentally about creating supportive, inclusive, and interconnected social systems that respect human dignity and potential across different cultures and societies. The results above were supported by several studies. Michalos et al. (2012) found that students exhibited high levels of favorable attitudes towards sustainable development which emphasized the importance of social justice, cultural understanding, and global collaboration. Similarly, Michalos et al. (2009) highlighted strong positive attitudes among both adults and students, emphasizing the societal aspects of sustainable development.

Additionally, *education* as a dimension of attitude towards sustainable development got a mean score of 4.23 or very high. This means that this dimension is always manifested. This implies that students consistently see sustainable development as grounded in transformative education that fosters critical thinking, global awareness, and adaptability, preparing young learners to tackle future challenges through innovative and holistic teaching methods. It can be deduced that sustainability education was already introduced in the basic education as Mazza (2021) emphasized the need for sustainability education starting from the basic education level. This attitude of the students suggests that teachers in the basic education are well-guided by UNESCO as it integrates sustainable development into primary and secondary education which includes lesson plans, teaching techniques, and assessment methods designed to foster sustainability awareness among young learners (UNESCO, 2012).

Further, *environment* got a mean score of 4.06 described as high. This means that *environment* as a dimension of attitude towards sustainable development is oftentimes manifested. This implies that students habitually emphasize environmental conservation as essential, advocating for balanced development that protects biodiversity and prioritizes ecological health over industrial and urban expansion, recognizing its vital role in human well-being and sustainable prosperity. This attitude suggests students see environmental sustainability not as an obstacle to development, but as a critical framework for responsible growth that ensures the quality of life for current and future generations, emphasizing the need to protect natural resources, maintain biodiversity, and implement more environmentally conscious agricultural and industrial practices.

Various studies highlighted the role of education in fostering sustainable development and pro-environmental behaviors. For example, Husaini et al. (2023) emphasize that integrating green education through the Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) framework can instill critical thinking and decision-making skills regarding environmental issues, ensuring ecological health and sustainability in schools. Similarly, it was found that hands-on environmental education activities in elementary schools improve students' awareness, sensitivity, and behavior toward conservation, which form the foundation for lifelong sustainable habits (Pambudi et al., 2022).

Additionally, Stevenson (2022) discussed critical socioecological approaches to sustainability education, advocating for collaborative and reflective learning that addresses sociocultural, ecological, and economic challenges holistically. This empowers students to engage in civic actions for a sustainable community. Early education efforts, such as teaching preschoolers about local natural resources, have also been shown to build awareness and responsible consumption habits from a young age (Žvinklienė & Miknevičienė, 2024).

Lastly, *economy* as a dimension of attitude towards sustainable development got a mean score of 3.98 or oftentimes manifested. This suggests that students perceive governments should prioritize sustainability, fairness, and global equity by promoting sustainable production, reducing resource waste, fostering fair trade, and addressing poverty and hunger over industrialized nations' economic gains. Sacrifices and increased spending are necessary to reduce inequalities and ensure long-term global well-being.

Students' recognition of economic fairness and sustainability as vital aspects of development is supported by several studies emphasizing education's role in shaping pro-sustainability attitudes Shaukat (2016) highlights that education for sustainable development (ESD) integrates social, environmental, and economic dimensions, teaching students to address global inequalities and resource management responsibly. This aligns with students' advocacy for equity and sustainable production (Shaukat, 2016).

Similarly, Kaya (2013) developed a scale to measure student attitudes towards sustainable development, identifying economic sustainability as a core dimension alongside environmental and social aspects. This indicates that students at basic education levels are capable of understanding the economic sacrifices needed to ensure long-term equity and sustainability. Furthermore, it was found that transformative sustainability education positively affects students' perceptions of economic fairness as a critical component of sustainable development, regardless of gender. This underscores the importance of embedding sustainability concepts into curricula to encourage future economic equity (Stewart, 2024).

Table 2. Attitude towards sustainable development, n=86

Indicators	\bar{x}	SD
Environment	4.06	0.591
Economy	3.98	0.635
Society	4.40	0.505
Education	4.23	0.615
Overall	4.17	0.487

Independent samples t-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by gender

Table 3 presents the independent samples t-test showing the differences in students' attitudes towards sustainable development. Data shows, in general, that there was a significant difference for gender, $t(84) = 3.666, p < .001$, as males ($\bar{x} = 4.40, SD = .40$) attained higher mean scores than females ($\bar{x} = 4.03, SD = .49$). The overall analysis of the table indicates that there is a significant difference in the attitudes towards sustainable development between male and female participants.

Table 3. Independent samples t-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by gender

Variables	Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	t	p
Environment	Male	33	4.30	.52	3.135	.002*
	Female	53	3.91	.60		
Economy	Male	33	4.21	.57	2.710	.008*
	Female	53	3.84	.64		
Society	Male	33	4.55	.40	2.247	.027*
	Female	53	4.31	.54		
Education	Male	33	4.53	.44	3.733	<.001*
	Female	53	4.05	.64		
Overall	Male	33	4.40	.40	3.666	<.001*
	Female	53	4.03	.49		

* $p < 0.05$

The significant differences observed in the mean scores for each statement indicate that males, on average, may hold different perspectives and values than females. According to Torbjörnsson et al. (2011) study, there were significant differences in how male and female students viewed sustainability, especially in issues related to solidarity and equity. The research found that male students not only placed greater emphasis on ensuring equitable access to resources and supporting community wellbeing but also exhibited a greater overall knowledge about sustainable development.

F-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by religion

An analysis of variance was performed to analyze the differences in students' attitude toward sustainable development when categorized according to religion as shown in Table 4. Results shows that there was no significant difference of students attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed according to religion, $F(2, 83) = .661$. This means that students' attitudes toward sustainable development do not significantly differ based on their religion. It can be said that religion is not a factor influencing students' attitudes toward sustainable development. According to the study of Greeley (2014), his findings show through his comparison report that religion and environmental concern show no significant differences. Additionally, a study from Truelove and Joireman (2009) has found a negative relationship between environmental attitudes and affiliation with certain religions, also indicating that religion is not a factor that influences students' attitude towards sustainable development.

Table 4. F-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by religion

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Between Groups	.201	2	.100	.661
Within Groups	19.983	83	.241	
Total	3451.65	85		

* $p < 0.05$

Independent samples t-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by age

Table 5 presents the results of independent samples t-test examining differences in students' attitudes toward sustainable development by age. The data indicates that there was no significant difference based on age, $t(84) = -.075, p = .940$, with 11-year-

olds ($\bar{x} = 4.16, SD = .41$) scoring slightly lower on average than 12-year-olds ($\bar{x} = 4.17, SD = .57$). This suggests that factors other than age may not significantly influence attitudes toward sustainability.

The overall result from the table suggests that there is no significant difference in how 11-year-olds and 12-year-olds perceive attitudes on sustainable development. According to Dietz et al. (2011), who examined age differences in environmental attitudes among European adolescents, age may not be the primary determinant of sustainability attitudes. Their findings imply that factors such as education and socio-economic background could play more significant roles in shaping these attitudes. Similarly, research from the National University of Malaysia indicates that while students may fairly assess sustainability in their school, their attitudes are not strongly influenced by age (Kwami et al., 2015).

However, there was a significant difference of students' attitude toward sustainable development in terms of society when analyzed according to age, $t(84) = 2.008, p = .048$. It was found that younger students ($\bar{x}=4.50, SD=.43$) have higher mean score than older students ($\bar{x}=4.28, SD=.57$). This suggests that younger individuals may have a more idealistic or optimistic outlook on social equity and sustainability. Winter (2008) emphasized that younger individuals, particularly teenagers, often exhibit greater enthusiasm for sustainability due to exposure to modern education methods and their formative understanding of global challenges.

Similarly, Rydzewski (2017) noted that age significantly affects attitudes toward societal issues in sustainable development, with younger respondents demonstrating stronger inclinations toward equity, inclusivity, and global responsibility, likely due to their educational environment promoting these values. Paschenko (2022) further highlighted that the younger generation's participation in educational modules focused on sustainable development fosters their understanding of global societal issues, emphasizing interdependence and civic responsibility. In contrast, older students may adopt more pragmatic attitudes shaped by life experiences and societal constraints, explaining their lower mean scores.

Table 5. Independent samples t-test results showing the differences of students' attitude toward sustainable development when analyzed by age

Variables	Group	n	\bar{x}	SD	t	p
Environment	11 years old	47	3.99	.52	-1.183	.240
	12 years old & above	39	4.14	.67		
Economy	11 years old	47	3.91	.60	-1.098	.275
	12 years old & above	39	4.06	.67		
Society	11 years old	47	4.50	.43	2.008	.048*
	12 years old & above	39	4.28	.57		
Education	11 years old	47	4.26	.53	.407	.685
	12 years old & above	39	4.21	.71		
Overall	11 years old	47	4.16	.41	-.075	.940
	12 years old & above	39	4.17	.57		

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were derived:

The level of attitude towards sustainable development among the respondents is high. The study revealed that the students exhibit a high level of positive attitude toward sustainable development. This indicates that students oftentimes value sustainable development and frequently manifest this in their actions. These actions often translate into real-world behaviors, such as reducing waste, conserving energy, and advocating for environmental policies.

The strong commitment to sustainable development among these students implies that they are not only aware of environmental issues but are also actively making choices that support a healthier planet. This finding is significant, as a positive attitude plays a vital role in fostering sustainable development. Moreover, it suggests that students are highly aware of sustainable development and are likely to engage in eco-friendly practices and support green initiatives.

In analyzing students' attitudes toward sustainable development, notable variations were noted based on gender, indicating that gender is a factor in the students' attitudes on sustainability. Conversely, the disparities observed among religious groups appear to be random, leading to the conclusion that students' attitudes on sustainable development do not differ significantly. Additionally, there is uniformity in students' attitudes towards sustainable development across different age groups.

Recommendations

After a careful review of the conclusions, the following recommendations were offered:

To address the significant difference in attitudes towards sustainable development between male and female students, interventions are implemented to bridge this gap and foster a more equitable understanding and engagement with sustainability. It is highly suggested that the faculty and teachers should focus on reducing and nurturing the gender gap in sustainable development attitudes. Additionally, while the research indicates that religion does not significantly differ students' views on sustainability, it is crucial to acknowledge and respect diverse religious perspectives. Elementary schools may create a comprehensive and interactive learning environment that instills a profound comprehension and commitment to sustainable development in students. Cultivating positive attitudes towards sustainability from a young age lays the groundwork for future generations to become well-informed, proactive, and responsible global citizens who contribute to a more sustainable and fair world.

Elementary schools may build a holistic and engaging learning environment that instills a deep-rooted understanding and commitment to sustainable development in students. Nurturing positive attitudes towards sustainability from an early age sets the stage for future generations to become informed, active, and responsible global citizens who contribute to a more sustainable and equitable world.

Parents are encouraged to actively engage in sustainable practices and discussions at home. Parents can involve children in activities such as recycling and composting. They can also discuss sustainability-related topics, read books on environmental issues, and explore nature together. By modeling sustainable behaviors and engaging in meaningful conversations, parents can inspire their children and reinforce the importance of sustainable development.

For future researchers that will be going to conduct research related to this study and can contribute to the growing body of knowledge on attitudes towards sustainable development, conduct studies that track attitudes towards sustainable development over an extended period. This will provide insights into the stability or changes in attitudes over time and help identify factors that influence these changes. They can also explore other demographic factors, such as educational background or socioeconomic status, to see if they have a more pronounced effect on sustainable attitudes among students.

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